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Review Article

Nanotechnology's Significance In The Treatment Of Viral Illness And Their Future Prospective With Emerging Patents

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ABSTRACT

The potential benefits and drawbacks of nanotechnology in viral therapy are like two sides of a coin. Many illnesses may now be better understood and treated with the help of nanomaterials. Lung cancer, TB, pulmonary fibrosis, and many more disorders can be treated with drug delivery systems based on nanoparticles. The primary killer on a global scale is infectious illnesses. Furthermore, there is a significant risk to public health from the adverse consequences of long-term usage and the fast development of drug resistance to existing therapies. Consequently, it is critical to find new therapeutic options. Diagnostics and treatment are two areas that stand to gain greatly from the ways in which nanostructures interact with diseases. An ideal vehicle for medication delivery would be nanoparticles due to their one-of-a-kind physicochemical characteristics. Properties such as a large drug payload capacity, an appropriate surface charge that can encapsulate, a high surface area to volume ratio that improves solubility relative to bigger particles, and a small particle size influence bioavailability and circulation time. In this article, we will take a look at how different nanotechnologies are being used to treat common viral diseases.

INTRODUCTION

“Infectious viruses pose a threat to global health because they impact millions of individuals and have a chilling impact on people's physical and social well-being [1]. Particles of dimensions inside the nanoscale range are the focus of nanotechnology, which involves their creation and application [2]. Research into the connections between nanotechnology and living organisms is

known as nanobiotechnology. Nanomedicine, on the other hand, is focused with diagnosing, treating, and preventing illness through the use of nanostructured materials [3]. There are a number of mechanisms via which nanoparticles are known to exert their antiviral effects. To begin, nanoparticles are attractive therapeutic agents for treating viruses due to their unique properties.

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Some of these characteristics include: (1) a tiny particle size, which makes it easier to distribute drugs to specific areas of the body (2) The ability to accommodate large drug payloads due to its high surface-to-volume ratio and the fact that its surface charge can be adjusted to facilitate cellular entry across negatively charged cellular membranes are crucial features [4]. Nanoparticles' ability to mimic biological processes, resulting in innate antiviral effects, has also been proven. To illustrate this point, consider dendrimers and silver nanoparticles [5]. Encapsulating medications, functionalizing them through the construction of stable structures, or altering them to provide optimal dosage and drug delivery [6] are all possible by enhancing stability and drug retention periods. Lastly, it is thought that building nanoparticles with targeting moieties to maximise selectivity to specific tissues, cell types, or subcellular compartments might substantially improve drug delivery [7]. Treatment of infected hosts and subsequent viral elimination presents a number of difficulties. For instance, reservoirs can be found in beneficial cellular and anatomical places, such as the blood-brain barrier (BBB) and the blood-testis barrier [8].”

A few examples of biocompatible systems:

Any nanomaterial with the potential to treat disease is referred to as a nano pharmaceutical, including dendrimers, liposomes, micelles, and nano-capsules [9]. They can serve as therapeutic agents, with the drug either being dissolved, entrapped, encapsulated, adsorbed, or chemically bonded [10]. Nanoparticles can be categorised based on their structure, chemical makeup, and ability to distribute medications, as well as the properties of the matrix from which they are made.

Organic nanoparticles:

The most commonly accepted approach for therapeutic usage in humans is organic nanoparticle therapy, which has been the subject of the most comprehensive research in the field of

drug delivery nanoparticles [11]. The following list of organic nanoparticle kinds includes the most popular ones.

Polymeric nanoparticles:

“The size range of polymeric nanoparticles, which are solid colloidal particles, is 10 to 1000 nm. Higher concentrations at the target locations may be attained because to the tiny size, which allows cells to more readily enter and absorb capillaries [12]. The FDA and WHO have given their stamp of approval to many polymers for usage in medicines and medical items, including poly(lactide-co-glycolides), polylactides (PLA), and polyglycolides (PGA). The best nanoparticles for these applications are those made of poly(D,L-lactide-co-glycolide) (PLG) or poly(L-lactic acid-co-glycolide) (PLGA), which are both biocompatible and biodegradable. The use of hydrophilic polymer surface modifications, like PEG, is essential for minimising non-specific interactions with serum proteins, lowering opsonization susceptibility, and postponing phagocytosis uptake. This is the "gold-standard" of cloaking agent systems because it delays absorption, which increases the drug's half-life and changes its biodistribution and pharmacokinetic profile even more. Polymeric nanoparticles may be classified into two main types: nanospheres and nano capsules [13].

Nanocapsules:

“The medication is housed in an interior chamber of a hollow sphere called a nanocapsule, which is coated with a polymer [14]. Their size can vary from 50 to 300 nm, and they are characterised by a low density and a high loading capacity [15]. One mechanism by which nanocapsules can improve medication distribution is through the permeability glycoprotein (P-gp) efflux transporter, which could explain why antiviral drugs do not reach brain tissue to the same extent. To improve drug distribution across the BBB, an excipient known as Solutol® HS15 can block P-

gp. Findings demonstrated that Solutol® HS15 nanocapsules loaded with the HIV protease inhibitor, indinavir, significantly increased absorption in the brain and testes of mice compared to control animals who received only indinavir solution [3].

Nanospheres:

These matrix structures, with diameters between 100 and 200 nm, physically or evenly distribute the medicine. The use of nanospheres in the treatment of influenza, herpes simplex virus (HSV), and hepatitis B virus (HBV) has been the subject of several research projects. Reviews of their use in viral treatment are very extensive [16].

Liposomes:

Liposomes are 20–30 nm in diameter and shaped like spherical carriers. Phospholipid bilayers encase an aqueous core; these bilayers mimic cell membranes and can fuse directly with microbial membranes [17]. The phospholipid bilayer and the inner aqueous cavity are two potential entry points for drugs or other substances with biological activity. Liposomes are advantageous since they are biodegradable and mostly harmless. The potential of liposomal formulations to function as immunological adjuvants has led to much research into their use in vaccine development [18].

Micelles:

Sizes of micelles range from 10 to 100 nm. Encased in a hydrophobic core, which may include drugs with low water solubility (such as PEG, which might prolong circulation and promote accumulation), they have an exterior hydrophilic polymer [19]. An example of this is polymeric micelles, which have recently attracted a lot of interest as a potential medication delivery mechanism. Medications that are now technologically constrained owing to their low solubility in water and instability can have their water solubility and stability improved using polymeric micelle drug encapsulation, a highly promising nanotechnology. Due to their slower

dissociation rate compared to other therapeutic agents, micelles are able to retain drugs for a longer period of time and accumulate more medicine at the desired site [20].

Dendrimers:

“The symmetrical, macromolecular, and hyper-branched terminal groups of dendrimers govern their interaction with their target environments. Through the use of connectors and branching units [21], these groupings radiate outward from a central core. In addition to a spherical core, these structures also have branches and terminal functional groups. Their versatility and value are enhanced by their capacity to include various chemical moieties, possess several inner layers, and exhibit diverse surface groups (multivalent surface) [22]”.

Solid

lipid nanoparticles: “In addition to the more typical colloidal nanoparticles, another method of drug administration is solid lipid nanoparticles, or SLNs. Combining the benefits and drawbacks of traditional nanocarriers is one objective of SLN use. To prove a point, SLNs are far more practical for drug delivery than polymeric nanoparticles because of how much easier and cheaper they are to produce in large quantities. Additional advantages of SLNs over synthetic polymer nanoparticles include improved drug-release patterns, higher stability, safety, and availability, and lower toxicity [23-24]”.

Inorganic nanoparticles:

“Metallic nanoparticles, which can range in size from 1 to 100 nm, are smaller than their organic counterparts yet exhibit significantly higher loading efficiency. The "bottom-up" approach involves constructing the nanoparticle from the smallest building blocks (e.g., atoms or clusters) and the "top-down" method involves reducing the size of the inorganic material to the nanoscale. Both methods are used to create metallic nanoparticles [25]. Reaction variables (pH,

temperature, time, or concentration) can alter nanoparticle size and shape, and reducing agent choice impacts loading capacity, release, and aggregation profiles, among other things [26].

Gold nanoparticles:

Because of their biocompatibility, accessible production procedures, variety in surface modification, and good conductivity, gold nanoparticles (GNPs) are undergoing intensive research as nanocarriers. Thanks to their photophysical characteristics, which allow for effective drug release at remote places, and the many functionalization choices provided by thiol linkages, these nanoparticles possess unique physical and chemical features in addition to an inert and non-toxic gold core. Nanoparticle sizes can vary from 1-2 nm, 1.5-5 nm, or 10-150 nm, depending on the application, and can be produced using simple GNP synthesis procedures [27-28].

Silver nanoparticles:

The most efficient metallic nanoparticles against bacteria, viruses, and other eukaryotic microorganisms are silver nanoparticles due to their high conductivity, catalytic capabilities, chemical stability, and intrinsic inhibitory and antibacterial powers of silver [29]. Nanoparticles of silver primarily function by causing DNA damage, rupturing cell membranes, and releasing silver ions, which enhance antibacterial activity. The reader is advised to read up on the topic of silver nanoparticles as virucidal agents [30].

Other metallic nanoparticles:

Metal nanoparticles (copper, zinc, and titanium, for example) or metal oxides (iron, zinc, and titanium dioxide) can target viruses in particular ways. There are some that still need more research, such as the platinum nanoparticles used to identify the flu virus. The fundamental spherical core of a core-shell nanoparticle is surrounded by an outer shell made of a different material. The outer shell can be bimetallic or monometallic as well. Research has demonstrated that various core-shell

nanoparticle shapes may be utilised in the field of biomedicine [31-32].

Antiviral nanotherapeutics

Nano-vaccines:

“Nanovaccinology can be used as an adjuvant to boost the immune system and has potential use in both therapeutic and preventative measures [33]. The limitations of traditional immunisations, such as limited immunogenicity, inherent in vivo instability, toxicity, and the need for frequent doses, might be circumvented using this technique, which offers several advantages over conventional vaccine creation [34]. Reducing the size of nano-based vaccines improves their humoral and cellular immune response by increasing absorption by phagocytic cells, gut-associated lymphoid tissue, and mucosa-associated lymphoid tissue. Better antigen presentation and detection are the results that follow. Utilising nanoparticles in vaccine formulations also has the added benefit of allowing for the controlled and prolonged release of adjuvants or antigens [35].

Nanoparticle uptake:

The therapeutic load and, thus, the correct dosage entering the cells are determined by uptake, making it crucial to design nanotherapeutics with uptake in mind. The efficiency of the uptake process can be affected by variations in the nanoparticles' physical properties as well as those of the cell membrane [36]. Cells that are unable to phagocytose are the most efficient in absorbing microparticles (nanoparticles) with a diameter of 50 nm or less [37]. Improving cellular uptake is possible with the use of diverse ligands, which may be peptides or proteins. One well-known peptide that can help in cellular penetration is the TAT peptide, which is produced by the HIV virus. The ability of a nanoparticle to penetrate a negatively charged cell membrane is proportional to its total surface charge, hence raising this charge increases absorption across cellular membranes [38].

Antigenicity:

Synthetic compounds have the ability to activate the four pathways (lytic, classical, alternative, and lectin) that make up the immune system's complement system. [39] The conventional complement route relies on the formation of antigen/antibody complexes, in contrast to the other pathways, which do not need antibodies. To restrict their value in vivo, some nanocarriers including carbon nanotubes and immunoliposomes can activate the complement system. This can result in the opsonization or clearance of foreign nanomaterials.

Nanoparticle biodegradation and elimination:

As the range of nanoparticles and the medicinal uses for them grows, the need to understand how they biodegrade becomes greater. Furthermore, biodegradation mechanisms have a substantial impact on attributes of biodistribution and extended drug release [40]. A comprehensive examination of the pharmacokinetics of nanoparticle absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion will lead to better and more rational drug design. Particle size, molecular weight, polymer composition, tacticity, and hydrophobicity/hydrophilicity profiles are some of the factors that might affect the degradation rate. However, there is a lack of information from in vivo studies and very little focus on nanoparticle disintegration at the cellular level [41-42].

Limitations of nanoparticles as therapeutics:

“The inability to apply certain crucial therapeutic treatments could be due to the limited permeability of biological membranes [43]. Not all cell types possess the necessary machinery to carry out any of the endocytotic processes, which further limits the uptake and medicinal uses of nanoparticles. Phagocytosis, macropinocytosis, endocytosis mediated by clathrin and caveolin, and endocytosis independent of both clathrin and caveolin are all processes that fall under this category [44]. The internalisation of foreign

materials is known as non-specific cellular uptake, which is characterised by a lack of material selectivity [45]. The use of nanoparticles as therapeutic agents is severely constrained by their non-specific absorption by macrophages, the primary immune system cell, and reticuloendothelial system organs such the liver and spleen. This event causes the nanoparticles to be removed from circulation before they reach the target areas, decreasing the effectiveness of the treatment [46]. Two common approaches to avoiding non-specific interactions are coating the surface of nanoparticles with PEG molecules of an optimum molecular weight and employing active targeting ligands.”

Nanoparticle requirements that are unique to viral infections:

“In their interactions with host cells, obligatory intracellular parasites like viruses often participate in a wide range of receptor-ligand interactions. Because viruses have complex life cycles, different replication dynamics, the potential for latent infection in inaccessible biological compartments, multiple steps of replication in different subcellular compartments or organelles, and the rise of drug resistance, they present unique challenges to drug development. Nanotechnology has demonstrated its worth in pharmaceutical applications, particularly in cancer therapy, with the aid of several commercially available drugs, such as Caelyx® and Doxil®. However, chemotherapeutic treatments have a major drawback: they aren't tumour specific, so patients have to take dangerously large doses of medication to get enough of them [47]”. “Getting the right dose of the right medicine to the right place at the right time is essential for any therapeutic treatment to work [48]. There are two different ways to target. When inflammation or cancer causes the local circulatory system to become more permeable, passive targeting may occur. As a result, the nanotherapeutic material can more

readily accumulate in the afflicted area. To be directed to specific receptors, epitopes, or locations, nanotherapeutics must be coupled to a ligand in active targeting. A ligand might be an antibody or peptide. Because the mechanism of action of antiviral medications and the stage of viral replication dictate that they localise at certain sub-cellular locations or organelles, active targeting is a key element of viral infection treatment. To provide an example, the nucleus is the sole place where integrase inhibitors may impede the strand transfer mechanism that HIV employs. Hence, it is preferred to employ active targeting methods, such as incorporating a nuclear localization signal onto the nanocarrier, in order to enhance specificity [49-50]. Premature drug release has far-reaching consequences for the treatment of intracellular and systemic illnesses. Nanoparticles' exceptionally long half-lives, in comparison to more traditional treatments, make delay and continual release both possible. In order to keep medicine concentrations within the therapeutic window and reduce the possibility of drug resistance, controlled and sustained release is an additional crucial component [51-52].

Application of Nanotechnology

Applications of Nanotechnology in Different Industries

After thorough and careful analyses, a wide range of industries—in which nanotechnology is producing remarkable applications—have been studied, reviewed, and selected to be made part of this review. It should be notified that multiple subcategories of industrial links may be discussed under one heading to elaborate upon the wide-scale applications of nanotechnology in different industries. A graphical abstract at the beginning of this article indicates the different industries in which nanotechnology is imparting remarkable implications, details of which are briefly discussed under different headings in the next session.

Nanotechnology and Computer Industry

Nanotechnology has taken its origins from microengineering concepts in physics and material sciences. Nanoscaling is not a new concept in the computer industry, as technologists and technicians have been working for a long time to design such modified forms of computer-based technologies that require minimum space for the most efficient work. Resultantly, the usage of nanotubes instead of silicon chips is being increasingly experimented upon in computer devices. Feynman and Drexler's work has greatly inspired computer scientists to design revolutionary nanocomputers from which wide-scale advantages could be attained. A few years ago, it was an unimaginable to consider laptops, mobiles, and other handy gadgets as thin as we have today, and it is impossible for even the common man to think that with the passage of time, more advanced, sophisticated, and lighter computer devices will be commonly used. Nanotechnology holds the potential to make this possible. Energy-efficient, sustainable, and urbanized technologies have been emerging since the beginning of the 21st century. The improvement via nanotechnology in information and communication technology (ICT) is noteworthy in terms of the improvements achieved in interconnected communities, economic competitiveness, environmental stability during demographic shifts, and global development. The major implications of renewable technology incorporate the roles of ICT and nanotechnology as enablers of environmental sustainability. The traditional methods of product resizing, re-functioning, and enhanced computational capabilities, due to their expensiveness and complicated manufacturing traits, have slowly been replaced by nanotechnological renovations. Novel technologies such as smart sensors logic elements, nanochips, memory storage nanodevices, optoelectronics, quantum computing, and lab-on-a-chip technologies are

important in this regard. The application of nanotechnology in computers cannot be distinguished from other industrial applications, because everything in modern industries is controlled by a systemic network in association with a network of computers and similar technologies. Thus, the fields of electronics, manufacturing, processing, and packaging, among several others, are interlinked with nanocomputer science. Silicon tubes have had immense applications that revolutionized the industrial revolution in the 20th century; now, the industrial revolution is in yet another revolutionary phase based on nanostructures. Silicon tubes have been slowly replaced with nanotubes, which are allowing a great deal of improvement and efficiency in computing technology. Similarly, lab-on-a-chip technology and memory chips are being formulated at nano scales to lessen the storage space but increase the storage volume within a small, flexible, and easily workable chip in computers for their subsequent applications in multiple other industries [53]. Hundreds of nanotechnology computer-related products have been marketed in the last 20 years of the nanotechnological revolution [54]. Modern industries such as textiles, automotive, civil engineering, construction, solar technologies, environmental applications, medicine, transportation agriculture, and food processing, among others are largely reaping the benefits of nano-scale computer chips and other devices. In simple terms, everything out there in nano industrial applications has something to do with computer-based applications in the nano industry [55-57]. Thus, all the applications discussed in this review more or less originate from nano computers. These applications are enabling considerable improvement and positive reports within the industrial sector. Having said that, it is hoped that computer scientists will remain engaged and will keep on collaborating with

scientists in other fields to further explore the opportunities associated with nano computer sciences.

Nanotechnology and Bioprocessing Industries

Scientific and engineering rigor is being carried out to the link fields of nanotechnology with contributions to the bioprocessing industry. Researchers are interested in how the basics of nanomaterials could be used for the high-quality manufacturing of food and other biomaterials [58]. Pathogenic identification, food monitoring, biosensor devices, and smart packaging materials, especially those that are reusable and biodegradable, and the nanoencapsulation of active food compounds are only a few nanotechnological applications which have been the prime focus of the research community in recent years. Eventually, societal acceptability and dealing with social, cultural, and ethical concerns will allow the successful delivery of nano-based bio-processed products into the common markets for public usage [59]. With the increasing population worldwide, food requirements are increasing in addition to the concerns regarding the production of safe, healthy, and recurring food options. Sensors and diagnostic devices will help improve the sensitivity in food quality monitoring [60]. Moreover, the fake industrial application of food products could be easily scanned out of a system with the application of nanotechnology which could control brand protection throughout bio-processing [61]. The power usage in food production might also be controlled after a total nanotechnological application in the food industry. The decrease in power consumption would ultimately be positive for the environment. This could directly bring in the interplay of environment, food, and nanotechnology and would help to reduce environmental concerns in future [62]. Moreover, the advancement of nanotechnology has also been conferred to the development of functional food items. The

exposure and integration of nanotechnology and the food industry have resulted in larger quantities of sustainable, safer, and healthier food products for human consumption, which is a growing need for the rising population worldwide [63]. The overall positive impact of nanotechnology in food processing, manufacturing, packing, pathogenic detection, monitoring, and production profiles necessitates the wide-scale application of this technology in the food industry worldwide [64-65]. Recent research has shown how the delivery of bioactive compounds and essential ingredients is and can be improved by the application of nanomaterials (nanoencapsulation) in food products. These technologies improve the protection performance and sensitivity of bioactive ingredients while preventing unnecessary interaction with other constituents of foods, thus establishing clear-cut improved bioactivity and solubility profiles of nanofoods, thereby improving human health benefits. However, it should be kept in mind that the safety regards of these food should be carefully regulated with safety profiling, as they directly interact with human bodies [66].

Nanotechnology and Agri-Industries

Agriculture is the backbone of the economies of various nations around the globe. It is a major contributing factor to the world economy in general and plays a critical role in population maintenance by providing nutritional needs to them. As global weather patterns are changing owing to the dramatic changes caused by global warming, it is accepted that agriculture will be greatly affected [67]. Under this scenario, it is always better to take proactive measures to make agricultural practices more secure and sustainable than before. Modern technology is thus being employed worldwide. Nanotechnology has also come to play an effective role in this interplay of sustainable technologies. It plays an important role during the production, processing, storing,

packaging, and transport of agricultural industrial products [68]. Nanotechnology has introduced certain precision farming techniques to enhance plant nutrients' absorbance, alongside better pathogenic detection against agricultural diseases. Fertilizers are being improved by the application of nanoclays and zeolites which play effective roles in soil nutrient broths and in the restoration soil fertility [69]. Modern concepts of smart seeds and seed banks are also programmed to germinate under favorable conditions for their survival; nanopolymeric mixtures are used for coating in these scenarios [70]. Herbicides, pesticides, fungicides, and insecticides are also being revolutionized through nanotechnology applications. It has also been considered to upgrade linked fields of poultry and animal husbandry via the application of nanotechnology in treatment and disinfection practices.

Nanotechnology and Food Industry

The applications of nanotechnology in the food industry are immense and include food manufacturing, packaging, safety measures, drug delivery to specific sites [71], smart diets, and other modern preservatives, as summarized in Figure 1. Nanomaterials such as polymer/clay nanocomposites are used in packing materials due to their high barrier properties against environmental impacts [72]. Similarly, nanoparticle mixtures are used as antimicrobial agents to protect stored food products against rapid microbial decay, especially in canned products. Similarly, several nanosensor and nano-assembly-based assays are used for microbial detection processes in food storage and manufacturing industries [73]. Nanoassemblies hold the potential to detect small gasses and organic and inorganic residues alongside microscopic pathogenic entities [74]. It should, however, be kept in mind that most of these nanoparticles are not directly added to food species because of the risk of toxicity that may be attached to such metallic nanoparticles.

Work is being carried out to predict the toxicity attached, so that in the future, these products' market acceptability could be increased [75]. With this, it is pertinent to say that nanotechnology is rapidly taking steps into the food industry for packing, sensing, storage, and antimicrobial applications [76]. Nanotechnology is also revolutionizing the dairy industry worldwide [77]. An outline of potential applications of nanotechnology in the dairy industry may include: improved processing methods, improved food contact and mixing, better yields, the increased shelf life and safety of dairy-based products, improved packaging, and antimicrobial resistance [78]. Additionally, nanocarriers are increasingly applied to transfer biologically active substances, drugs, enhanced flavors, colors, odors, and other food characteristics to dairy products [79]. These compounds exhibit higher delivery, solubility, and absorption properties to their targeted system. However, the problem of public acceptability due to the fear of unknown or potential side effects associated with nano-based dairy and food products needs to be addressed for the wider-scale commercialization of these products [80].

Nanotechnology, Poultry and Meat Industry:

The poultry industry is a big chunk of the food industry and contributes millions of dollars every year to food industries around the world. Various commercial food chains are running throughout the world, the bases of which start from healthy poultry industries. The incidence of widespread foodborne diseases that originate from poultry, milk, and meat farms is a great concern for the food industry. Nanobiotechnology is certainly playing a productive role in tackling food pathogens such as those which procreate from Salmonella and Campylobacter infections by allowing increased poultry consumption while maintaining the affordability and safety of manufactured chicken products [81]. Several nano-based tools and materials such as nano-

enabled disinfectants, surface biocides, protective clothing, air and water filters, packaging materials, biosensors, and detective devices are being used to confirm the authenticity and traceability of poultry products [82]. Moreover, nano-based materials are used to reduce foodborne pathogens and spoilage organisms before the food becomes part of the supply chain [83].

Nanotechnology—Fruit and Vegetable Industry:

As already described, nanotechnology has made its way far ahead in the food industry. The agricultural, medicinal, and fruit and vegetable industries cannot remain unaffected under this scenario. Scientists are trying to increase the shelf life of fresh organic products to fulfil the nutritional needs of a growing population. From horticulture to food processing, packaging, and pathogenic detection technology, nanotechnology plays a vital role in the safety and production of vegetables and fruits [84]. Conventional technologies are now being replaced with nanotechnology due to their benefits of cost-effectiveness, satisfactory results, and overall shelf life improvement compared to past practices. Although some risks may be attached, nanotechnology has not yet reported high-grade toxicity to organic fresh green products. These technologies serve the purpose of providing safe and sufficient food sources to customers while reducing postharvest wastage, which is a major concern in developing nations. Nanopackaging provides the benefits of lower humidity, oxygen passage, and optimal water vapor transmission rates. Hence, in the longer run, the shelf life of such products is increased to the desired level using nanotechnology [85].

Nanotechnology and Winemaking Industry:

The winemaking industry is a big commercial application of the food industry worldwide. The usage of nanotechnology is also expanding in this industry. Nanotechnology serves the purpose of

sensing technology through employment as nanoelectronics, nano-electrochemical, and biological, amperometric, or fluorimetric sensors. These nanomaterials help to analyze the wine components, including polyphenols, organic acids, biogenic amines, or sulfur dioxide, and ensure they are at appropriate levels during the production of wine and complete processing [86]. Efforts are being made to further improve sensing nanotechnology to increase the accuracy, selectivity, sensitivity, and rapid response rate for wine sampling, production, and treatment procedures. Specific nanoassemblies that are used in winemaking industries include carbon nanorods, nanodots, nanotubes, and metallic nanoparticles such as gold, silver, zinc oxide, iron oxide, and other types of nanocomposites. Recent research studies have introduced the concept of electronic tongues, nanoliquid chromatography, mesoporous silica, and applications of magnetic nanoparticles in winemaking products [87]. An elaborative account of these nanomaterials is out of the scope of the present study; however, on a broader scale, it is not wrong to say that nanotechnology is successfully reaping in the field of ecology.

Nanotechnology and Packaging Industries

The packaging industry is continuously under improvement since the issue of environmentalism has been raised around the globe. Several different concerns are linked to the packaging industry; primarily, packaging should provide food safety to deliver the best quality to the consumer end. In addition, packaging needs to be environmentally friendly to reduce the food-waste-related pollution concern and to make the industrial processes more sustainable. Trials are being carried out to reduce the burden by replacing non-biodegradable plastic packaging materials with eco-friendly organic biopolymer-based materials which are processed at the nano scale to incur the beneficial properties of nanotechnology [88]. The nanomanufacturing

of packaging biomaterials has proven effective in food packaging industries, as nanomanufacturing not only contributes to increasing food safety and production but also tackles environmental issues [53]. Some examples of these packaging nanomaterials may include anticaking agents, nanoadditives, delivery systems for nutraceuticals, and many more. The nanocompositions of packing materials are formed by mixing nanofillers and biopolymers to enhance packaging's functionality [89]. Nanomaterials with antimicrobial properties are preferred in these cases, and they are mixed with a polymer to prevent the contamination of the packaged material. It is important to mention here that this technology is not only limited to food packaging; instead, packaging nanotechnology is now also being introduced in certain other industries such as textile, leather, and cosmetic industries in which it is providing large benefits to those industries.

Nanotechnology and Construction Industry and Civil Engineering

Efficient construction is the new normal application for sustainable development. The incorporation of nanomaterials in the construction industry is increasing to further the sustainability concern. Nanomaterials are added to act as binding agents in cement. These nanoparticles enhance the chemical and physical properties of strength, durability, and workability for the long-lasting potential of the construction industry. Materials such as silicon dioxide which were previously also in use are now manufactured at the nano scale [90]. These nanostructures along with polymeric additives increase the density and stability of construction suspension [91]. The aspect of sustainable development is being applied to the manufacture of modern technologies coupled with beneficial applications of nanotechnology. This concept has produced novel isolative and smart window technologies which have driven roots in nanoengineering, such as vacuum insulation

panels (VIPs) and phase change materials (PCMs), which provide thermal insulation effects and thus save energy and improve indoor air quality in homes [92]. A few of the unique properties of nanomaterials in construction include light structure, strengthened structural composition, low maintenance requirements, resistant coatings, improved pipe and bridge joining materials, improved cementitious materials, extensive fire resistance, sound absorption, and insulation properties, as well as the enhanced reflectivity of glass surfaces [93]. As elaborated under the heading of civil engineering applications, concrete's properties are the most commonly

discussed and widely changing in the construction industry because of concrete's minute structure, which can be easily converted to the nano scale [94]. More specifically, the combination of nano-SiO₂ in cement could improve its performance in terms of compressiveness, large volumes with increased compressiveness, improved pore size distribution, and texture strength [95].

Recent patent on nanotechnology

The most particular information about patented technology for lemongrass oil applications. These databases can provide current information on granted patents and patent applications globally.

Patent No.	Inventor	Filed On	Title	Ref.
EP2714017B1	Liangfang Zhang Ronnie Hongbo FANG Che-ming HU (jack) Jonathan COPP	2012-05-24	Membrane encapsulated nanoparticles and method of use	[96]
JP6820225B2	Samuel, Jayakumar, Ponsamboju, Narasimha, Chariyau, Kerum, Wai. Webb, Stephen, Earl. Burrows, Frank, G.	2017-04-03	Use of dendrimer nanotechnology to deliver biomolecules to plant cells	[97]
AU2005330718B2	Francesco Stellacci Arum Amy Yu	2005-04-12	Nanocontact printing	[98]
US8540939B2	Krisztián Niesz Atilla Wootsch Maxime Groualle Zsolt Ötvös Ferenc Darvas	2009-04-28	Instrument and process for nanoparticles production in continuous flow mode	[99]

FUTURE PROSPECTIVE

In recent years, significant research has been carried out regarding application of nanomaterials in the detection and diagnosis of viruses. However, due to the close similarity of nucleic acid sequences of some viruses, the clinical false positive rate of some detection methods is still high, resulting in misdiagnosis and waste of resources. A recent review reported the false-negative rates from 2 to 33% in repeat sample testing from COVID-19 suspects [100]. Therefore,

improving the specificity of clinical diagnosis using nanotechnology is need of the hour. Although considerable efforts have been made in the development of therapeutic schemes for different viruses, yet there are few drugs that effectively inhibit viruses, with the exception of vaccines. In the virus tracking process, although QDs have shown excellent optical brightness and light stability, they still have limitations such as their larger size, flicker and potential interference with the function of viruses. In addition, the extent

to which QD markers might affect the true behavior of viruses in living cells is not clear. Thus, SVT will certainly benefit from the development of new types of smaller and non-flickering QDs to avoid these restrictions. During viral infection, a variety of interactions occur between host cells and viruses. Super-resolution imaging makes it possible to depict exactly this kind of cellular process on a nanoscale. The super-resolution methods, which have optical resolution from 20 to 100 nm, can unveil the mechanism of virus infection in subcellular environment satisfactorily, and make possible revelation of the potential mechanism of virus infection by decomposing the subvirus. New imaging technology is still needed to combine SVT and super-resolution microscopy to capture and quantitatively understand the basic processes involved in virus infection with nano spatial resolution. SVT is limited to the *in vitro* study of virus infection mechanisms. By tracking individual viruses in living tissues and animals, it is possible to analyze the process of virus transmission between cells and understand how viruses break through the host's defense barrier. So far, several research groups have reported non-invasive visualization of mice viruses [101-102]. Due to the limitations of current bioimaging techniques, tracking a single virus *in vivo* in real time is still a challenge. Recently, near-infrared QDs with emission ranges of 800–1600 nm were synthesized and are of particular interest in the production of ~2 nm size ultra-small near-infrared QDs via quasi biosynthesis [103-107]. With collaboration between scientists all over the world development of smaller, non-toxic, and chemically stable nanomaterials could be achieved in near future. These novel and robust NPs would contribute to unravel the virus infection mechanisms with higher precision and accuracy, both *in vivo* and *in vitro*, supporting the

development of antiviral drugs and vaccines, consequently to curb the mortalities [103-107].

CONCLUSION

A lot of people are interested in using nanoparticle-based delivery systems to treat viral infections because they provide new approaches to overcoming issues with conventional treatment plans. Traditional antiviral properties, such as a tiny and controlled size, a high surface area to volume ratio, and the capacity to modify the surface with the prospect of multi-functionalization, may be integrated into nanomaterials through nanosystem-specific changes. As far as clinical and biological research is concerned, this is undeniably a helpful instrument. New advances in nanomedicine have the potential to be more therapeutically useful than older approaches. These include the ability to biocompatibly encapsulate or incorporate drugs, target drug delivery (intracellularly or to specific cell populations), and achieve slow and sustained drug release. These changes can circumvent typical problems with biomedical nanoparticles, such as reduced toxicity profiles, increased biological membrane permeability, and associated selective absorption. In a similar vein, nanocarriers can be used to improve the solubility and stability of drugs that are unstable or just weakly soluble in water in physiological conditions.” The potential for (1) multi-functionalization to achieve drug delivery and imaging simultaneously (using, for example, a fluorescent signal), (2) multiplexing to simulate multiple diseases at once, and (3) specific cell/tissue/compartments targeting (using, for example, targeting ligands like peptides and proteins or molecular recognition strategies) should be investigated in future studies. To further improve the present conventional antivirals (by increasing bioavailability and lowering toxicity), research into nanotechnology advancements is also required. We have already established that "nanotraps" effectively inhibit influenza viruses.

The particular modification of the attachment carbs of the designated host receptors allows for the expansion of this to include other viruses, such as hepatitis, HIV, and so on. This can only be accomplished with more research and development of these particles. At a time when medication resistance is a serious problem, the use of nanotechnology to combat infectious illnesses has great potential for either enhancing the efficacy of existing treatments or inspiring the development of whole new ones. There needs to be more study into the toxicity and possible negative effects of certain nanosystems before we can fully appreciate the advantages of these nanoparticles over traditional pharmaceuticals.”

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